

ISic1449

I.Sicily inscription 1449

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. τῷ Διὸς τῷ Μ
2. ἔλιξιῶ ἐμὶ
3. πρῶτὰ Εὐμε
4. νίδῶ τῷ Πε
5. διάρχῶ

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 494020

EDR 120706

EDCS 41300044

PHI 175655

PHI 329929

PHI 330100

Bibliography

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